

Face Recognition System Based on Wavelet Transform, Histograms of Oriented Gradients and Support Vector Machine

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Abstract—Face recognition is a well-known image analysis application in the fields of pattern recognition and computer vision. It utilizes the uniqueness of human facial characteristics for personnel identification. The paper in hand presents a facial recognition system that uses facial features and Support Vector Machine (SVM) to achieve accurate recognition. The image processing happens with histogram equalization, also utilizing a median filter for pre-processing. A combination of wavelet transforms and Histograms of Oriented Gradients (HOG), extracts the feature vector, which produces a reliable performance. Dimensionality reduction happens by applying Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Finally, by applying the Support Vector Machine (SVM), face classification happens. Experimental development happened on the Yale database of 165 images from 15 individuals in a MATLAB environment. The testing proved the accuracy of 98.64% percentage of success with acceptable speed, and it confirmed the accuracy and robustness of the proposed system.

Keywords— Face recognition; Wavelet transform; HOG; PCA; SVM;

I. INTRODUCTION

Face recognition distinguishes itself to be one of the eminent applications in analyzing images in the branches of pattern recognition and computer vision. This technology depends on the variation of facial characteristics. A variety of fields in modern life use facial recognition, such as security systems, video retrieval, passport, and credit cards. The extraction of the characteristics of face images and the selection of a suitable classifier are two essential technologies to solve the problems of face recognition. Facial features can differentiate persons depending on their distinct characteristics. The appearance of an individual can change due to lighting conditions, illumination variations, different emotions, pose variations, and ageing factors during image acquisition, all of these aspects affect the appearance of a person and make it hard to be recognized [1-4].

For the processing of facial images, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is commonly used, which takes advantage of characteristic features called “Eigenfaces”. Eigenfaces try to create a “principal component” image from the training set by aligning the mouth, eyes, and other facial features of the subjects in the scanned images, where the gallery and probe images must be normalized and in the same size. Then, to

reduce the dimensionality of data applies a method of image compression, which reduces the structure to the lowest, yet useful, facial pattern [5].

Any irrelevant information is dropped after this reduction, and the facial structure is decomposed into uncorrelated (orthogonal) components previously identified as eigenfaces. The characterization of each facial image happens as a weighted sum feature vector of eigenfaces, stored in a one-dimensional array, which will result in a two-dimensional array for a set of gallery images. The comparison of a probe image ensues with the gallery image by computing the distance between their feature vectors then disclosing the matching result. This linear method is popular in appearance-based approaches for face recognition, which aims to solve the problem of recognition within a representation area of a lower dimension than the image area [6].

The Histograms of oriented gradients Feature (HOG) introduced by Dalal and Triggs [7]. Histograms of oriented gradients (HOG) descriptor, inherited from scale-invariant feature transforms, performs quite well on human detection. Dalal and Triggs [7] initially proposed the HOG descriptor. Their work proves the HOG descriptor is robust in representing humans.

Support vector machine (SVM) has proved its ability to reach better recognition results than various other generative classifiers, due to the small amount of data required for training [8]. It has set the focus on the field machine learning, being the youngest part of the statistical learning theory as it is still in the stage of development [3].

II. LITERATURE OVERVIEW

Hua Wang [9], have introduced a face recognition system based on Local Difference Binary (LDB) and HOG. The LDB and HOG methods are applied to extract the local pattern features and edge features of face images, and The SVM is applied as a classifier. M. Awais et al. [10], have introduced a face recognition Real-time surveillance system through face recognition. The HOG techniques are applied to extract the face features of face images, and Feedforward Neural Networks are used as a classifier. Bairagi, Das, Chatterjee, and Tudu [11], presented face recognition of invariant expressions by depending on the detection of the fiducial points through using SURF with a Gabor filter. The performance of the presented method is more reliable than the conventional

SURF algorithm. S. Hua, G. Chen, H. Wei, and Q. Jiang [12], presented a robust face recognition method. They used a SURF algorithm to extract the vectors of the feature with pose invariance and scale invariance from face images. PCA is then used to produce a new feature space as PCA-SURF, which is local to the SURF feature vectors. Finally, the implementation of the K-means algorithm clusters the feature points and classifies the face images by combing the global and local similarity. Gumus E., Kilic N., Sertbas A. and Ucan O. [13], used various face recognition feature extraction techniques, including the wavelet decomposition and Eigenfaces method, which is PCA-based. After generating feature vectors, the classification stage uses SVMs and a distance classifier.

The order of this paper is as follows: Section III shows the architecture of the proposed system. Section IV discusses the experiments and results. Finally, Section V mentions the conclusions.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A definition of three stages explains the proposed system: In the first stage, histogram equalization and median filtering adjust intensities of the images and filter noise. The second stage uses a combination of wavelet transform and HOG to extract features from the images. In the third step, PCA reduces the dimension of the image, and SVM classification happens to extract the dimensionally reduced features. The chart below describes the third stage:

Fig. 1. Overview of the system

A. Pre-processing

Pre-processing is the initial and most crucial step in the face recognition system because it affects the results of the next steps. Requiring the application of two techniques: a median filter, which removes noise from the image, and the implementation of histogram equalization to enhance the contrast of the image.

B. Histograms of oriented gradients

HOG descriptor is a local statistic orientation of the image gradients around a critical point. To be precise, each of the descriptors is a bundle of histograms composed of pixel

orientations given by their gradients. The reference to the number of possible orientations is "No". Each histogram in the bundle defines a specific area around the key point. These areas correspond to the cells centered at the critical point of an $N_p \times N_p$ squared grid. HOG feature extraction contains four steps [14]:

- 1) Gradient computation is the first step to compute the gradient values by applied 1D derivative masks for the vertical and horizontal directions.
- 2) Orientation binning is the second stage in the HOG method. Depend on the number of values attained in the gradient calculation, every pixel within the cell casts a weighted vote for a histogram channel depending on the orientation.
- 3) Descriptor blocks: The gradient's strengths must be normalized locally to account for the changes in illumination and contrast, requiring a grouping of cells into larger and spatially connected blocks.

4) Block normalization: cell histograms require to be normalized to minimize the effect of changes in the contrast within images of the same object. furthermore, overall gradient magnitude does offer some information, and normalization over a block a region greater than a single cell preserves some of this information, namely, the relative magnitudes of gradients in cells in the same block. Since up to four blocks cover each cell, possibly representing each histogram up to four times with up to four different normalizations.

C. Wavelet Transform

Wavelet transform is one of the most popular and useful feature extraction and decomposition methods applied to a plethora of applications. It is employed to convert the images to the frequency domain by applying a low pass and a high pass filter. It divides the input image into the four sub-bands (LL, LH, HL, and HH). The mathematical formulation of DWT is shown in an equation below [15]:

$$\varphi_{(i,j)}(x) = 2^{\frac{i}{2}} \varphi(2^{-i}x - l) \quad (1)$$

Where x indicates the variable, s , and l describe the integers that scale and stretch the function to produce wavelets. The utilization of one stage of DWT extracts features from the input image.

D. Principal Component Analysis

After the feature's extraction, a PCA method extracts the facial features using Eigenfaces, let a face image $I(x, y)$ be an N by N two-dimensional array of 8-bit intensity values. The main idea of PCA is to find the feature vectors within the entire image space. Let the $\Gamma_1, \Gamma_2, \Gamma_3 \dots \dots \Gamma_M$ be the images training set of the face; the average set is well-defined by $\psi = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M \Gamma_n$ where the distance between each face and the average is $\Phi_i = \Gamma_i - \psi$ vector. Then subjecting this set to PCA commences the search for a set of M orthonormal vectors u_n that best defines the distribution of data. Choosing the k^{th} vector u_n such that:

$$\lambda_k = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M (u_k^T \Phi_n)^2 \quad (2)$$

Is to be maximized subject to:

$$u_l^T u_k = \delta_{lk} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } l = k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The λ_k are the eigenvalues and vectors u_k are eigenvectors of the covariance matrix:

$$C = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{n=1}^M \Phi_n \Phi_n^T = AA^T \quad (4)$$

Where $A = [\Phi_1 \Phi_2 \dots \Phi_M]$, the matrix C . However, is N^2 by N^2 , and determining the N^2 eigenvectors and eigenvalues is an intractable task for typical image sizes. Furthermore, taking the appropriate linear combinations of the face image Φ_i , by considering the eigenvectors v_i of AA^T such that:

$$A^T A v_i = \mu_i v_i \quad (5)$$

By multiplying both sides by A:

$$AA^T A v_i = \mu_i A v_i \quad (6)$$

Then the $A v_i$ are the eigenvectors of $C = AA^T$. Constructing $L_{mn} = \Phi_m^T \Phi_n$ following the analysis of the M by N matrix $L = A^T A$. Then finding the M eigenvectors v_l of L . These vectors measure linear combinations of the M training set of the face images to form the eigenfaces v_l :

$$u_l = \sum_{k=1}^M v_{lk} \Phi_k \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (7)$$

The calculations largely decrease with this analysis, from the order of several pixels in the images N^2 to the order of the number of images in the training set M [16, 17].

E. Support Vector Machine

SVM is a supervised learning algorithm in classification and regression purposes, consider separating data into two different classes with N points such that: $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ and $y_i \in \{-1, +1\}$. Where x_i represents the N -dimensional vector while y_i represent the class label of the vector. A hyperplane is used in SVM to separate the points of the two classes:

$$W^T x + b = 0 \quad (8)$$

Where x represents the vector, b is the bias, and w is an adaptive weight vector; this hyperplane functional margin is as follows:

$$W_0^T x_i + b_0 \geq +1 \rightarrow y_i = +1 \quad (9)$$

$$W_0^T x_i + b_0 \leq -1 \rightarrow y_i = -1 \quad (10)$$

by taking one point W_0 and b_0 , represents the geometrical distance of a point x as:

$$d(w_0, b_0, x) = \frac{|w_0 x + b_0|}{\|w_0\|} \quad (11)$$

SVM tries to maximize the distance between the closest points of these two classes with the hyperplane, so the best separation of the data is the one that minimizes the distance as:

$$\phi(W) = \frac{1}{2} \|W\|_2^2 = \frac{1}{2} (W \cdot W') \quad (12)$$

Maximizing the dual Lagrange formula obtains the optimization of the problem :

$$Q(\alpha) = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_i \alpha_j y_i y_j (x_i \cdot y_j) \quad (12)$$

Lagrange multiplier must subject to the constraints:

$$\alpha_i \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i y_i = 0 \quad (13)$$

Only a small number of α_i is none zero, which corresponds to one training data point. These data points lie on the border of the margin and are called Support Vectors [18-19].

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

The proposed approach implemented uses MATLAB 2018a. Using the Image processing toolbox, computer vision system toolbox and statistics, and machine learning toolbox to build the program. All simulated experiments used a personal computer with Core i5-2540M CPU 2.6 GHz and 8 GB of memory running under the Windows 7 operating system.

The proposed system uses three steps: (1) Pre-processing, (2) feature extraction, and (3) classification. A combination of wavelet transforms, and HOG methods extract the features. PCA then reduces the dimension of the image, and SVM classifies the extracted features. Fig. 2. shows the first two principal components of the features.

Fig. 2. The first two principal components

These experiments applied the HOG method to calculate the system performance using the Yale database [20]. The Yale database comprises of 11 different images for 15 persons under different light, exposure, and perspective. The images are 243 x 320 of the pixel's resolution with 265 grey levels per pixel, in the figure below shows a sample of those images.

The database has two sets, a train, and a test set. The experiment takes seven images of class one (S1) to class thirteen (S13) from the train set of images. On the other hand, the experiment selects the remaining four images of class one (S1) to class thirteen in addition to all eleven images in class fourteen (S14) and fifteen (S15) as test images. In this way, the experiment uses 91 images for training and 74 images for testing.

In the testing process, the methodology to prove face recognition firstly uses test images where the results are known previously as a benchmark to prove functionality. Then the same methodology is tested on some new images to consider the robustness, accuracy of the methodology. The performance measures are shown in the table below:

TABLE I. DISPLAY THE RESULTS OF STATISTICAL MEASUREMENT PARAMETERS ON THE TEST IMAGE

Method	Number of training samples	Number of testing samples	Accuracy
Proposal method	91	74	98.64 %

The benchmark outlined in this paper makes a comparison with three well-known methods implemented on the Yale database.

TABLE II. DISPLAY THE RESULTS OF STATISTICAL MEASUREMENT PARAMETERS ON THE TEST IMAGE

Method	Accuracy
Proposal method	98.64 %
Speeded up robust features method	65.277 %
Local Methods Using CCA [21]	97.14%
LBP method	91.43%
Gabor Wavelet method	90.47%

V. CONCLUSION

This paper highlights the development of an accurate and robust system for facial recognition in the MATLAB environment. Crucially, face recognition happens by the application of three distinct steps: (1) Pre-processing, (2) feature extraction, and (3) classification. When several face images are processed and tested, the system identifies the person. The result proved that combining pre-processing, feature extraction, and classification produces better results with acceptable speed. The combination of histograms of oriented gradients, principal component analysis, and the Support vector machine is useful for facial recognition systems.

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